

Grant agreement no.	101138451
Project acronym	PERSEPHONE
Project full title	Autonomous Exploration and Extraction of Deep Mineral Deposits
Dissemination level	PU Public
Date of Delivery	30 06 2025
Deliverable Number	D8.2
Deliverable Name	Realistic simulation worlds for integrated testing of PERSEPHONE technologies
AL / Task related	T8.2
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Keywords	Realistic simulations, Subterranean environments, gazebo simulations
Abstract	This deliverable presents the development and integration of realistic simulation environments to support the testing and validation of PERSEPHONE technologies. These environments, built using ROS2 and Ignition Gazebo, enable safe and repeatable evaluation of robotic exploration,

manipulation, and drilling operations in realistic subterranean scenarios.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under the Grant Agreement No.101138451

History of Changes

Version	Date	Reason of change
0.1 (draft)	01 June 2025	The initial draft of the document is ready and ready for distribution between PERSEPHONE project partners to review.
V0.5	20 July 2025	Final draft ready to be reviewed
V1.0	30 July 2025	Final version ready

Executive summary

This document (D8.2) outlines the development of realistic simulation environments for integrated testing of PERSEPHONE's robotic systems, supporting the goals of WP8. The simulations enable validation of perception, planning, and control algorithms in realistic underground scenarios created from both industrial (e.g. GM, KGHM) and field-collected data. A comprehensive ROS2-Gazebo-based architecture has been developed to allow for autonomous task simulation with multiple robot agents. Key features include visual ore textured meshes, modular robot configurations, and terrain-aware autonomy testing capabilities. The deliverable also presents the integration of change detection interms of tunnel structure and risk-aware planning frameworks evaluated across multiple realistic mine variants. Finally, future directions are proposed to improve photorealism and geometric detail in simulation environments.

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1 Abbreviations

Abbreviations	
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
DLO	Direct LiDAR Odometry
DOF	Degrees of Freedom
ECS	Entity-Component System
GM	Grecian Magnesite
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
KGHM	KGHM Polska Miedź S.A.
LAS	LiDAR Aerial Survey
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
ML	Machine Learning
MTL	Material Template Library
NUC	Next Unit of Computing
OBJ	Object file format
RGB	Red Green Blue
RGB-D	Red Green Blue + Depth Camera
ROS2	Robot Operating System version 2
SDF	Simulation Description Format
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
STAGE	Semantic Topological Autonomy Guidance Engine
UR	Universal Robot
URDF	Unified Robot Description Format

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose and scope of the document

The purpose of this document is to describe the development, configuration, and use of realistic underground mining simulation environments designed for the integrated testing of PERSEPHONE's robotic technologies. These environments are a core outcome of Task 8.2 and serve as a crucial tool for advancing and validating the project's autonomous exploration and extraction capabilities.

The simulations aim to replicate underground mining conditions as closely as possible, leveraging real-world Lesar point cloud data, terrain geometries, and robot models. These simulation environments will enable safe, repeatable, and scalable testing setup for autonomy algorithms prior to field deployment. This approach ensures that hardware-in-the-loop testing is grounded in realistic conditions, allowing teams to reduce the risk of direct deployments, refine autonomy logic, and accelerate iterative development cycles.

Specifically, the document outlines:

- The system architecture of the simulation framework, including robot models, control stacks, and automation features
- The process of creating simulated mining environments based on real-world data (e.g., from Grecian Magnesite and KGHM mines), including point cloud conversion, texture mapping, and integration into the simulator
- The configuration of simulation scenarios for multi-agent collaboration, risk assessment, and dynamic mission execution
- The evaluation of the STAGE planner and change detection pipeline within the simulated environments
- The future directions for improving simulation realism, including higher-fidelity meshes, RGB point cloud, and real-time risk simulations.

This deliverable contributes to the broader WP8 objectives by enabling the development, integration, and testing of PERSEPHONE's technologies in controlled, high-fidelity virtual environments that reflect operational challenges faced in deep and abandoned mines. It also forms a foundation for open sourcing the simulation environment beyond the project, potentially serving as a public benchmark platform or testbed for future autonomous mining research community.

2.2 Related documents

This deliverable builds on concepts, requirements, and system-level specifications defined in:

- D1.1:** High-level system architecture for autonomous exploration and drilling
- D1.2:** Use-case definitions and operational scenarios

D2.3: Conceptual design of the robotic subsystems, including drilling, exploration, and manipulation agents

D4.1, D4.2, D4.3, D4.4 and **D4.5:** Exploration and mapping simulations, semantic mapping, autonomous alignment, and coordinated robot behavior

3 Gazebo based Underground Mining Environments

3.1 Simulation Architecture

To create an autonomous fleet of robots that can perform autonomous tasks, a simulator is needed to simulate robots in realistic environments prior to deployment. This environment helps to develop all the algorithms and test them in a controlled scenario similar to the real one.

3.1.1 Simulator choice

Different maps can be loaded in a simulator building realistic environments by modelling material and texture. The map can be captured in real life with sensors (lidar, camera, etc.) and then imported as a virtual world representing physics accurately. In addition, robots can be built in these virtual worlds acting as they do with real hardware. Simulated robots can also carry simulated sensors (lidar, camera, force sensors, imu, etc.) which provide data to develop and test the algorithms for the autonomous stack.

First, we need to decide which simulator to use. The three most popular robotic simulators are Gazebo, Unity, and Isaac Sim. Each of them offers different advantages and tradeoffs.

Gazebo is the most widely used open-source robotics simulator. It provides direct integration with ROS and ROS2, which facilitates algorithm development. It supports multiple physics engines (ODE, Bullet, DART, ...) enabling realistic interactions between the robot and the world. Virtual worlds can be imported from real point-cloud data allowing accurate simulations. Gazebo provides a lot of plugins to simulate sensors needed for autonomous navigation (Lidar, IMU, RGB and Depth Cameras, ...) as well as other types of sensors like force sensors. There are plenty of robotic platforms available ready to use (like Universal Robots manipulators), but it is also possible to use custom robots by using URDF (Universal Robot Description Format) and SDF (Simulation Description Format). It also supports multi-robot simulation allowing to test coordinated fleet operations.

On the other hand, Unity is a high-performance game engine that can be adapted for robotics simulations. Its main advantage is the exceptional rendering quality, which can be useful for getting image data from cameras. However, it lacks native ROS2 support, requiring a ROS-TCP connector for communication. Unity's PhysX-based physics engine is designed for real-time game environments rather than high fidelity interaction simulations. Additionally, sensor simulation is limited, and developers must create custom scripts or rely on third-party plugins to simulate Lidar, IMU, or force sensors. Unity also does not support URDF natively.

Finally, Isaac Sim is a powerful simulator optimized for AI-driven robotics applications, leveraging GPU-accelerated physics and ray-traced sensor simulations. It provides ROS2 integration. Isaac Sim supports realistic Lidar and camera models, but it requires specific hardware from Nvidia, making it

hardware-intensive and less accessible. While it offers multi-robot simulation, it is optimized for AI training.

A comparison table with the different features they offer can be seen in Table 1. Among the three simulators, Gazebo stands out as the best choice for developing multi-robot simulation in mine environments due to its native ROS2 support, realistic physics simulation, sensor plugins accessibility, and ability to import real-world mine environments from point clouds. Unlike Unity, it offers force-based physics for drilling and terrain interaction, and unlike Isaac Sim, it does not require extensive GPU hardware. Gazebo’s active open-source community, flexibility in custom robot modeling, and robust sensor support make it the most practical and effective solution for this project.

Table 1: Overview of different Physics-based simulation engines

Feature	Gazebo	Unity	Isaac Sim
ROS2 Integration	Native support	Requires ROS-TCP connector	Strong ROS2 integration
Physics	Good Physics	Basic physics	Good physics
Sensors	Available robotic sensors	Requires custom plugins	Available robotic sensors
Custom robot models	Support URDF/SDF	No native support for URDF/SDF	Support URDF
Rendering	Basic, not focus on visuals	High-quality	High-quality
AI Integration	Limited	Well-suited for ML training	Optimized for deep learning
Ease of use	Well documented	Steep learning curve for robotics	Requires NVIDIA ecosystem
Hardware	Runs on standard hardware	Runs on most systems	Requires NVIDIA GPUs ¹²³

3.1.2 Gazebo architecture

Gazebo Sim follows a client-server architecture, as shown in Figure 1. The backend server runs simulation and physics, while the frontend client allows simulation visualization and interaction. Below is a description of the core components of Gazebo Sim to define a simulation.

Servers

The backend server runs a physics engine, sensor data processing, and simulation logic. It uses an Entity-Component System (ECS) to define objects and their properties, handling interactions between different simulation elements (e.g., robot dynamics, sensors). It includes default and custom plugins that extend functionalities, such as physics engines or sensor processing.

Figure 1: Gazebo Sim Architecture

Client

The front-end client provides the Graphical User Interface (GUI) for visualization and interaction of all simulated entities. It communicates with the server using Gazebo Transport and Messages to receive simulation updates and send commands. It also supports GUI plugins to customize the user experience.

Worlds

The simulation world will be the virtual environment with which all entities interact. The virtual world can be created from scratch (e.g., primitive shapes, or CAD models) or imported from real-world sensor data (e.g., LIDAR scans). The world is written as an SDF (Simulation Description Format) file, an XML-based format that specifies the elements in the simulation including lighting, gravity, and physical properties (e.g., friction).

Models

To represent any object or robot in the world, models are used. These models are defined in URDF (Universal Robot Description Format) files, an XML-based format that allows us to define a set of links (bodies) and joints (e.g., revolute, prismatic, fixed) to create entities. This file can include collision properties, mass, and inertia to simulate realistic physics interactions.

Sensors

Sensor plugins allow you to simulate real-world sensors such as LIDAR, cameras, IMUs, force sensors, and more. They generate synthetic data from the virtual world allowing to test algorithms. Sensors can also be configured with noise models to mimic real sensors.

3.1.3 Simulated Robot Fleet and Automation Framework

To validate the autonomous mission pipeline in realistic underground environments, a comprehensive Gazebo-based simulation framework has been developed. This environment replicates the behaviors of the full robot fleet, including exploration, manipulation, logistics, and drilling, by integrating custom and commercial platforms through modular ROS2 packages.

The robots included in the simulation are the ones defined in Deliverable 2.3 from WP where the conceptualization of deep drilling systems is defined. The simulated fleet consists of:

- **Terrain Hopper:** The vehicle has been implemented in simulation with the same control interfaces and motion behavior as the real one. It includes Ackermann steering and modular payload options, supporting accurate testing of navigation, autonomy, and manipulation tasks.
- **Stinger Robot:** This robotic driller has been replicated in simulation with all intended degrees of freedom, matching the physical structure and control logic. It enables realistic simulation of anchoring, body positioning, and drilling motions within confined tunnel environments.
- **UR10 Manipulator:** A standard industrial arm provided by Universal Robots, integrated directly from its ROS2 support package to ensure compatibility and fast transition between simulation and real hardware.
- **Robotiq Gripper:** A dexterous end-effector mounted on the UR10 for grasping operations.

Each robot is defined within its own ROS2 package, which follows a common structure:

- `urdf/`: Parameterized URDF (Unified Robot Description Format) files specifying geometry, kinematics, joints, sensors, and optional subsystems.
- `config/`: ROS2 control configurations for actuators and sensors.
- `launch/`: Automated launch files to initialize the robot, controllers, and its world-specific settings in Ignition Gazebo.

A key feature of this simulation framework is the ability to customize robot configurations at launch time to reflect their roles within the mission. This is primarily achieved using launch-time arguments and modular Xacro macros, enabling seamless creation of specialized agents from shared base models.

Terrain Hopper – Multi-role Mobile Base

The Terrain Hopper serves as the base for three robot agents, with modular components enabling different mission roles (ref Figure 2):

- **Exploration Robot:** The base configuration includes onboard sensors such as LiDAR, IMU, and RGB-D camera for mapping and localization. No additional payloads are mounted.
- **Deployer Robot:** By enabling the `ur` argument in the launch file, a UR10 manipulator is mounted on top. This setup supports deployment and rock characterization tasks.
- **Supplier Robot:** Activating the `bed` argument adds a rear platform to carry the Stinger Robot or other payloads. This configuration transforms the Terrain Hopper into a mobile logistics agent.

This modularity allows developers to instantiate any robot configuration on demand, using a single, unified URDF framework and launch interface.

Figure 2: Different robot agents that use Terrain Hopper as the mobile base. a) Exploration robot, b) Deployer robot, c) Supplier robot

Stinger Robot

The Stinger Robot is designed to simulate autonomous anchoring and drilling behaviors. The current prototype includes (ref. Figure 3):

- A central body with three actuated legs for surface anchoring.
- A simplified drilling unit consisting of rotating and prismatic joints, allowing the simulation of drill positioning and feed motion.

- ROS2 control interfaces for full joint-level trajectory control.

Although the full drilling mechanics are still under development, this prototype allows for realistic motion planning and integration testing. Force-torque sensors on the legs simulate anchoring feedback, and the drilling rig simulates depth progression into the rock surface.

Figure 3: Stinger robot simulation model deployed for drilling

Automation and Deployment

All robot configurations are launched through modular Python launch files that:

- Spawn the robot into a selected simulation world.
- Configure its controllers and sensors.
- Bridge simulation topics (e.g., IMU, force sensors, LiDAR) to ROS2 using `ros_gz_bridge`.
- Optionally enable autonomy modules like SLAM, Nav2, or behavior trees.

This setup enables launching entire fleets with one command, making it possible to evaluate coordinated behaviors across heterogeneous agents in controlled or randomized environments. Whether simulating a single robot or multi-agent collaboration, the infrastructure supports repeatable, scalable testing with minimal setup.

Figure 4 shows an automated simulation scenario used in WP4 D4.5 to perform autonomous drilling. The Deployer robot, the Supplier robot and the Stinger robot are spawned in the simulation world ready to start the mission.

Figure 4: Deployer robot and Supplier robot collaboration to perform autonomous drilling

Simulation visualization

The visualization framework has also been set up to be able to understand how the sensor data looks like, and the output of the different algorithms developed in WP4 are performing. Figure 5 shows Rviz visualization framework showing point cloud data (red points) from the vehicles.

Figure 5: Rviz visualization of the sensor data while robot moving through the tunnel

3.2 Realistic Mining Environment

3.2.1 Point-cloud to Mesh conversion

Figure 6 The quadruped robot in the muddy ground during UPAT's visit to the GM mine site.

GM site visit for Equipment Testing:

During M7, UPAT visited one of GM's mines in order to test a quadruped robot equipped with a 3D-LiDAR. An RGB-D camera with an IMU sensor were also used during the visit. The purpose of this visit was to obtain hands-on experience and to detect some of the conditions and challenges that a robot may encounter in an underground mining environment. Additionally, potential issues that may occur while receiving measurements from different sensors were considered.

Regarding the conditions of the mine it was noted that the ground was mostly muddy (Figure 6) and potentially slippery and that made the traversability of the quadruped robot difficult. Additionally, the presence of deep mud pits with depth ranging from 0.5m, up to 1m, posed a danger for the robot. The LiDAR sensor was unable to determine whether the ground ahead was solid or a mud pit. Furthermore, water leaking from the ceiling in the form of droplets presented a potential danger as it could damage exposed electrical and mechanical components of the quadruped robot.

In that particular mine, there were very low levels of dust, thus the LiDAR sensor's view wasn't obscured by dust particles. The mining site, also, contained parts of abandoned mines which aligned with the characteristics relevant to the PERSEPHONE project case study. Multiple photographs of the mine were taken

that depicted parts of the mine and, mainly, magnesite veins that were later used in the simulated environment.

Figure 7 Abandoned mine. In the walls surrounding the abandoned mine magnesite veins are visible.

All the findings from the visit to the site were then presented to the consortium meeting in Athens during M9.

Field Data Acquisition

A quadruped robot equipped with a 3D LiDAR, an RGBD camera, an IMU and a NUC PC was manually operated through the mine to cover as much area as possible given the battery life. Simultaneous localization and mapping was performed using the DLO (Direct LiDAR Odometry) framework. In the KGHM mine, a multispectral camera brought by GSB was also mounted on the robot, and multispectral images of the mine face were captured using a serial interface between the NUC and an Arduino connected to the camera.

Point Cloud Processing Workflow

- The pointcloud map was converted to a mesh by the following steps
- The dense pointcloud was subsampled to speed up the subsequent steps
- Surface normals were computed from it
- A polygonal mesh was generated using Poisson Surface Reconstruction
- The mesh was trimmed by thresholding on the point cloud density to remove unneeded polygons
- The conversion was carried out using the open source software Cloud Compare. The input pointcloud was in .laz format, and the output mesh in .obj format.

3.2.2 Mine Texture Integration

Laser scans and pointcloud data are useful resources for mapping an environment and defining the position of a mobile robot in said environment. However, real-world environments such as abandoned and deep mines require more information to be integrated into it such as the existence of ores and minerals which are not included in the laser scans and the pointcloud data. One way of representing this information is by adding visual characteristics to the environment in the form of 2D textures to the generated mesh that corresponds to the underground mine, since magnesite ore is visible and this feature could be used in simulations. These textures can be either generated from real data such as RGB, RGB-D or spectral camera images collected from actual mines or from pictures found online. Two versions currently exist in the different simulated environments created within this project that attempt to add the existence of magnesite in the walls of the mine. Both versions are depicted in Figure 8 and Figure 9. The first one (Figure 8) depicts the first integration of a 2D texture with painted white lines drawn over a picture of a rocky texture that are supposed to imitate magnesite veins. Figure 9 is the result of multiple pictures taken from the GM mine that have been edited in such a way to create a texture that when it is used in the

simulated environment, it will depict a vein of magnesite that leads to the identification of the potential drilling site.

After creating an environment with realistic textures, simulated visual sensors (RGB, RGB-D or spectral cameras, etc.) can be used to perceive this information for a variety of applications. One of those applications is visual servoing which can be useful for the alignment of the robot used for drilling at the mining face as it is mentioned in D4.5. Additionally, a textured environment can be used for semantic mapping, as it explained in D4.3.

White drawn line that represents magnesite veins

Figure 8 Early attempt of integrating a realistic texture to the mine that represents magnesite veins in the underground mine.

Real magnesite veins from pictures taken at the mine of GM

Figure 9 A more realistic integration of a magnesite veins texture on the simulated mine.

Figure 10 Image of the RGB camera of the Terrain Hopper in Gazebo showing the camera capturing the part of the mine with the magnesite vein texture.

3.2.3 Texture mapping process

The texture mapping process is a term originating from computer graphics. This process describes the method in which 2D images are projected on 3D models. More specifically in the case of the simulated mine, the mesh's faces that are created from the vertices of the mesh of the mine are projected onto the 2D images that represent the texture of the mine. This unwrapping of the 3D model into the UV space was done with the use of Blender, an open-source 3D computer graphics software. While the 2D texture images were created using GIMP (GNU Image Manipulation Program) which is a free and open-source raster graphics editor.

Figure 11 The UV unwrapping of the faces of the mine into the UV space where the texture for the realistic depiction of the magnesite vein is loaded. The edges of each face (triangle) are depicted with grey lines, while the vertices are depicted as black

3.2.4 Integration to Gazebo

To create the texturing of the mine, a “.blend” file was created, which contains all the necessary information of the project created in blender. However, this type of file format is not supported by Gazebo. Therefore, for the textured mesh to be imported to Gazebo, it is exported, using Blender, into a compatible format which is the “.obj” type file for the mesh of the environment and a “.mtl” file type that contains important information regarding texturing. “.mtl” files or, as they are mostly known as, material files contain information such as the lighting coefficients of the material as they are defined in the field of computer graphics, the coefficients regarding the transparency and the shininess of the object and the path to the image that is to be used as the texture. The “.obj” files or object files have information about the X, Y, Z coordinates of each vertex of the mesh, the U, V,

texture coordinates of the faces of the mesh, the vector normals of the vertices, the vertices that correspond to the formation of each face, the vertices that correspond in the formation of the lines of the mesh, as well as, additional information such as smooth shading and the name of the material file to be used for texturing. The command to load the object file of the mesh is included in the corresponding “.sdf” world file and when Gazebo parses the “.sdf” it loads the texture declared in the material file based on the U, V coordinates stated in the object file.

Proper definition of the material file parameters can create realistic textures that lead to realistic conditions on which the results of the simulated visual sensors can be tested. Such conditions can be poor lighting of the underground environment which can provide a challenge for the visual sensors to capture the information provided by the textures. Additionally, the textures used in the simulated

Figure 12 The texture of the simulated underground mine containing pictures with magnesite veins from real mines.

environment should be of high resolution so that they can depict the veins in the most realistic way possible. In case textures with poor resolution are used, the magnesite veins of the mine will not be able to be properly recognized from the Terrain Hopper’s visual sensors regardless of their own image capturing resolution.

4 Integrated Simulation Scenarios

4.1 Realistic simulations

4.1.1 Simulation for testing integrated autonomous deployment

To support the development and validation of the STAGE planner in the developed simulation platform, which enables full-stack autonomy testing and benchmarking in a safe and repeatable manner, without requiring immediate deployment in physical mines.

As part of this effort, we collaborated with our industrial partner Grecian Magnesite (GM), who provided detailed LAS-format 3D point cloud data from both the active production areas and the abandoned sectors of one of their mines. These high-fidelity datasets form the basis for constructing simulation environments that closely resemble the operational conditions and spatial constraints encountered by autonomous machines during real missions.

Figure 13: The original LAS scan from the GM mine is converted into a mesh format for further integration into gazebo as a simulation world.

Following are some of the results from the simulation while testing the developed STAGE planner. In this simulated environment, the STAGE planner is responsible for:

- Autonomous exploration of unknown areas
- Dynamic navigation to mine face waypoints
- Handling blockages and re-routing in real-time using simulated changes to the environment

This setup provides a valuable bridge between algorithmic development and real-world deployment, allowing for robust pre-validation of navigation capabilities under realistic mine-like conditions before transitioning to hardware testing in the field.

To evaluate the real-time performance and robustness of the STAGE planner in realistic underground settings, we conducted autonomous exploration trials using the converted 3D mesh of the Grecian Magnesite (GM) mine within the Ignition Gazebo simulation environment. These experiments were designed to simulate the mapping of previously unknown or abandoned areas of the mine using only onboard sensors and autonomy logic.

Figure 14: Snapshots from an autonomous exploration mission using the STAGE planner in the Grecian Magnesite (GM) mine simulation world (early phase). The machine begins to map its immediate surroundings, incrementally extending its explored area through local frontier navigation.

Figure 14 Figure 15 showcase a series of snapshots captured at regular time intervals during a single autonomous mission. The images visualize the incrementally built map as perceived by the robot while navigating and exploring the underground tunnels. The coloring encodes traversal progression, with each

panel highlighting the evolving coverage as the robot explores further into the mine's interior.

The exploration strategy employed here is a hallmark of the STAGE planner's design: a bifurcated local-global exploration framework. The machine first builds local sub-graphs based on its real-time point cloud, using these to select and execute short-term exploration paths toward high-gain frontiers. However, once local exploration converges either due to a dead-end, low information gain, or visibility constraints the planner shifts into global re-positioning mode.

In this mode, the robot queries a global graph that encodes all previously explored frontiers and the interconnecting pathways between them. Using this structure, the robot computes global Dijkstra paths to reposition itself toward a distant, still-unexplored region of the mine what we refer to as a global frontier.

This alternation between focused local exploration and informed global repositioning ensures that the robot avoids becoming trapped in isolated areas, and instead steadily pushes the exploration boundary outward. The result is a highly efficient and autonomous mapping of large-scale, complex subterranean spaces, as demonstrated in the final frames of Figure 15, where the robot has covered a large, bifurcated region of the simulated mine.

Figure 15: Continued progression of the mission, showing large-scale mapping of the mine. As local frontiers become exhausted, the robot repositions to unexplored global frontiers via the global graph, resulting in bifurcated exploration patterns that maximize spatial coverage and information gain.

4.1.2 Simulations for rockfall or deformations in Underground mines

Multiple different environments have been created to simulate different scenarios. These mines are based on data gathered from the mines of GM and KGHM. The data gathered has been processed accordingly to create different environments that can be

Figure 16: Part of a tunnel of the simulated that has been deformed. The tunnel before the deformity can be seen in the top picture while the part of the tunnel deformed can be seen in the bottom picture

defined from their specific characteristics. Such characteristics can be deformities in the tunnels or rockfalls or a combination of the two. This is done to create an environment where risk assessment algorithms can be utilised as it is done in the premises of WP4. Mapping the multiple environment variants with the original and comparing the different maps generated using SLAM algorithms allow for the simulation of realistic scenarios where the robots pass from an area of the mine which has changed significantly over time and reassess the ability to traverse the previously traversable as well as assess the risk provided from that change.

Three variations of the mine were created. The first one includes rockfalls that completely block part of a tunnel of the mine and make it impossible for the mining machine used in the simulation to traverse through or around it.

Figure 1198: Blocked tunnel of the abandoned mine from rockfall in the simulated environment

The second variation contains a partially deformed part of the tunnel of the abandoned mine where the ceiling is lowered, and the overall cross section has been reduced. It is significantly harder for the ground vehicle to traverse.

Figure 19 18: The deformed tunnel in the second variant of the mine (left) and the same tunnel in the original simulated environment (right). With the red arrows the part of the ceiling that has been lowered can be observed while the blue arrows indicate the difference in the width between the two versions.

The third variation contains a partially deformed part of the tunnel in the same manner as in the second variation while it includes the addition of rockfall that partially blocks the tunnel.

Figure 20 20 Depiction of the third variant of the simulated environment that contains rockfalls and deformities (left). Depiction of the same part of the mine in the original simulated environment (right).

Results from Simulation Environment:

The developed change detection pipeline was evaluated using the three simulation-based scenarios provided by UPAT. These scenarios were specifically designed to test the system's sensitivity to structural deformation, object addition, and large-scale occlusions. The evaluation begins with the comparison between the reference map and the deformed tunnel map.

1) Deformed Tunnel

In this case, subtle geometric changes were introduced to the tunnel walls to simulate realistic structural deformation. As shown in the accompanying figures, the initial alignment step was successful in registering the deformed map to the original coordinate frame. Even at this stage, some of the deformation is visually discernible, providing a consistent spatial basis for change detection.

Figure 21: Aligned reference and deformed 3D point cloud maps, highlighting areas of partial deformation.

Following alignment, the pipeline performs its bi-temporal analysis and outputs two types of detected changes:

- Green-highlighted points represent parts of the map that no longer exist in the new scan, i.e., material or structure that has been displaced or deformed away.
- Red-highlighted points indicate newly introduced geometry, such as expanded bulges or newly visible surfaces caused by the deformation.

Figure 22: Result of the change detection pipeline. Green points indicate points removed from the reference map, while red points represent newly added points. Visible deformations are highlighted.

This dual-labeling scheme allows for an intuitive understanding of directional change: not just that change occurred, but how the structure evolved (removed vs. added material). As illustrated in the Figures 22 and 23, the system effectively localizes these changes along the altered tunnel sections and distinguishes between retained and newly appearing geometry.

Despite the sparse resolution of the simulated LiDAR scans and the use of conservative filtering to reduce noise, the system was able to detect meaningful deformations. Some fine-scale changes may be partially filtered, while occasional outliers persist, especially in low-density regions or near edges. These are expected limitations under current data fidelity, and will be addressed in future work by:

- Incorporating denser point clouds,
- Exploring adaptive voxel filtering strategies,
- And employing local surface fitting or confidence-based pruning.

A closer inspection of the point cloud maps shows visible changes in tunnel cross-section, confirming that the proposed method captures real geometric variance, not just noise artifacts. This is particularly promising for use cases where early

detection of tunnel expansion, collapse precursors, or instability indicators is critical for operational safety.

Figure 23: Detailed view of tunnel deformation highlighting red points identified by the change detection pipeline as additions compared to the reference map. Some outliers are present, attributed to mapping inaccuracies and partial sparsity of the map.

2) Deformed Tunnel and Rockfall

The second scenario introduces scattered rockfall debris into the tunnel, simulating a partial obstruction event. In this case, the topology remains largely similar to the original, but localized accumulations of material on the tunnel floor new navigation hazards.

Figure 24 : Visualization of the deformed tunnel, highlighting newly detected areas in red. Deformation is clearly visible towards the front, while rockfalls are observed further back.

After map alignment, the change detection framework identifies multiple small-volume changes concentrated towards the deformed portion of the tunnel. As in the previous scenario, the output highlights red regions where new material, such as rock clusters, has been introduced.

As shown in the Figures 25 and 26, the red points accurately correspond to the locations of added debris, while the green regions are sparser—indicating areas where previously observed surfaces are now occluded by the new material. This distinction is critical, as it allows inspection systems to distinguish between true object addition and line-of-sight occlusion, both of which are relevant for risk assessment.

Figure 25: Close-up view of tunnel deformation and rockfalls, with affected areas highlighted in red.

The system demonstrates good precision in identifying small but dense clusters of change, even when the surrounding structure remains unchanged. This is particularly important for operational scenarios where unexpected obstructions, such as minor rockfalls, may not significantly deform the tunnel geometry but can still impede robotic navigation or present physical hazards to human crews.

Some residual noise remains in areas near the boundary of the debris clusters, where sparse point coverage or marginal voxel occupancy can lead to ambiguous classification. However, the overall quality of detection remains consistent, and the performance is robust to these limitations.

This scenario validates the pipeline's sensitivity to localized topological additions and highlights its potential for monitoring obstruction growth over time. The method's ability to isolate even small-scale changes supports its use for early hazard detection and contributes to informed navigation or rerouting decisions within an autonomous inspection loop.

3) *Blocked Entrance*

The final evaluation scenario simulates a severe event in which the tunnel entrance is obstructed by large boulders, representing a full collapse or significant debris accumulation. This condition prevents the robot from accessing or mapping the tunnel beyond a certain point, effectively truncating the scan and occluding previously visible regions.

Following the alignment of the reference map and the obstructed map, the framework accurately identifies a large region of removed points beyond the point of collapse, highlighted in green. These represent structural areas that were visible in the original scan but are now absent due to the robot's inability to proceed past the blockage. This removed region serves as an implicit indicator of occlusion or inaccessibility.

Figure 26: Visualization of the blocked tunnel entrance. Red points indicate new blockage areas absent in the reference map, while green points represent areas removed from visibility due to obstruction during mapping.

In parallel, partial boulder geometry at the point of collapse is detected and highlighted in red, corresponding to newly observed surfaces not present in the reference map.

Figure 27: Detailed view highlighting changes in the reference map caused by the blockage.

This combination of red and green regions effectively communicates both:

- The presence of a physical blockage (via the added geometry), and
- The loss of previously mappable space (via the removed geometry).

Together, these two outputs capture the full impact of the collapse event both the structural addition (boulders) and the navigational consequence (lack of access beyond the obstruction). The system does not require prior knowledge of tunnel topology; it infers the hazard purely from observed deviations between routine scans.

While the internal structure of the blockage is only partially visible due to occlusion, the pipeline provides a strong, interpretable signal of critical change. This makes it suitable for integration into automated hazard alerts, especially in remote inspection scenarios where human intervention may be delayed.

4.2 Future integrations and beyond Persephone

The simulation environments are created mainly from two sources. The first is the mine partner provided a professionally generated LAS point cloud scan of the mine using ground truth systems. This scan is then converted to a mesh form to be imported inside the Gazebo simulation environments. The second source of the data is manually collected point cloud scans from the robot equipped with the LiDAR sensor. In this approach the operator has much deeper control on the SLAM system responsible for taking the instantons raw point cloud scan around the robot and accumulating it in a systematic way to create a global detailed map of the environment. The resolution of the final map can be tuned based on the on-board compute power, type of the sensor and the level of autonomy (if the data is collected in fully autonomous exploration mission or in a manual teleoperation manner).

However, during the evaluation phase a critical limitation of such data collection and simulation environment generation is observed. The absence of photo realistic texture inside the environment and the simplification of the mesh results in a relatively poor representation of the original terrain. As part of the future development effort, the project plans to investigate novel simulation environment generation approaches where the user can define the photo realistic texture not only in the post refinement phase but also through generating a detailed RGB color point cloud scans from photogrammetry. The future of the simulation environment creation pipeline also aims to remove the point cloud to mesh simplification phase where a lot of original terrain detail is lost in large triangles representing obstacles and non-uniform ground. This will significantly improve how the mobile ground robot platforms are evaluated for navigation in completely unknown environments.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable outlines the documentation of the creation and deployment of realistic simulation environments tailored for the integrated testing of PERSEPHONE technologies. Using Gazebo and ROS2, a modular, high-fidelity framework has been developed that supports full-stack testing of exploration, manipulation, and drilling systems in representative underground scenarios. The simulation environments incorporate real mine data, visual ore textured meshes, and deformable terrain to support a wide range of testing needs. These includes sensor emulation to multi-robot coordination and hazard detection. These simulations play a crucial role in bridging the gap between algorithm development and real-world deployment, enabling safe, repeatable testing before field trials. Ongoing and future improvements aim to further enhance realism and usability, particularly in texture realism and terrain resolution, to support increasingly advanced autonomy pipelines.